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TURNING VR INTO SOMETHING USEFUL. A CASE STUDY ON ELICITING REQUIREMENTS FOR VIRTUAL REALITY DESIGN TOOLS

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ABSTRACT

Advantageous applications of Virtual Reality (VR) in product design can be found throughout the product development process. For instance, VR can facilitate stakeholder communication or enable virtual prototyping. However, despite a wealth of literature describing opportunities of VR, and an accompanying range of VR toolkits, it has yet to become a common design tool. It is argued that the limited adoption of VR as a design tool is caused by the fact that most VR design tools are less accessible for product designers. The research presented in this paper aims to provide designers with VR design tools that are useful, usable and easily accessible. The approach involves three industrial case studies in which we first identify advantageous VR applications and then provide the industrial partner with tools to create this application. The resulting requirements are validated through a cross-company evaluation. This paper presents the results of the first case study.

Keywords: Virtual Reality, Design Tools, Case Studies

INTRODUCTION

A challenge inherent to the nature of design is the lack of concrete design information. Design information (e.g. product dimensions, cost estimations or user requirements) is either not yet available or scattered amongst stakeholders in a multidisciplinary design team. These challenges are particularly risky in the early stages of design, where major design decisions are to be made based on scarce, scattered and unreliable information (See Herstatt & Verworn, 2004, and Nobelius & Trygg, 2002)

End-user involvement can improve the information quality and quantity; end-user feedback for instance facilitates concept generation and selection, or identifies usability issues in an early stage. However, with only limited design information available it is difficult to provide end-users with a clear presentation of a product concept and future use context. We propose to use Virtual Reality (VR) technologies to create realistic concept representations in the early stages of a user centred design process.

VR technologies create an alternative reality in which worlds, objects and characters can be experienced that may not yet be available in reality. As such it allows end-users to not only *see* the future product (which could also be achieved with a concept sketch or mockup), but also *experience* the product and the interactions with its use context. However, despite a wealth of literature describing VR applications in the design process, and an accompanying range of VR development toolkits, it has yet to become a common tool amongst product designers.

We argue that the limited adoption of VR as a design tool is caused by the fact that most VR design tools and toolkits are oriented towards software engineers or researchers instead of product designers. Especially in the early stages of a design process, product designers can not be expected to invest time and effort in learning how to develop software or how to create complex 3D environments.

Our research aims to identify requirements for the development of *usable* and *useful* VR design tools for product designers. The requirements are derived from three industrial case studies, in which we first identify an advantageous VR application and then

provide the industrial partner with tools to create this application. This paper describes the identification of advantageous VR applications in the first case study, and shows how the definition of an application helps product designers with expressing more detailed design tool requirements.

VR IN PRODUCT DEVELOPMENT

Over the years VR technologies found their way into the realms of the product development process. In the early '90s VR mostly acted as a layer on top of well established CAD systems (Ottosson, 1998), either for visualisation (e.g. CAVE systems and head mounted displays) or as natural and immersive interfaces such as haptics and motion tracking (Weidlich et al, 2009). The substantial costs and a focus on large and complex data sets made VR primarily applicable in larger industries such as aerospace and automotive design.

Advancements in hardware and software reduced costs and extended the application scope of VR to simulation, training, prototyping and evaluation purposes (Jimeno & Puerta, 2007). These product design applications exploit the ability of VR to allow non-existing products or environments to be experienced in a natural and realistic way. This is beneficial when the real world situation is too dangerous (e.g. a drive simulator, as described by Tideman et al 2008), when an environment needs to be controlled (e.g. in simulation and evaluation as described by Kuutti et al, 2001) or when physical prototyping is too expensive or simply not possible yet (e.g. virtual prototyping, as described by Balcisoy et al, 2000).

The examples of advantageous applications of VR technologies in the product development process illustrate the substantial set of applications available for this field. To achieve adoption of these applications by industry at large, it is argued that industries need guidance on identifying and implementing VR in their design process. The work of Miedema et al, 2009, provides “*a decision support structure to assist in estimating the advantages of applying VR in company-specific use cases*” (focusing on small and medium sized enterprises). A 'man in the middle' approach is proposed, where a consultant matches company requirements with the most appropriate (determined by benchmarks) VR

technology. While this consultancy approach is able to inform the client company about which VR application to use and how it will contribute to the design process, it does not deliver the *tools* to actually create this application.

Successfully deploying VR applications in a product development process requires appropriate tools that match capabilities and requirements of the tool users (e.g. product designers) and fit in existing tool chains. The majority of existing VR design tools originates from research in computer science, and often consists of *toolkits* that extend programming languages with VR specific functions (see Wright and Madey, 2009 for an extensive survey). Examples include *VR Juggler* (Bierbaum et al, 2008), *OpenTracker* (Reitmayr & Schmalstieg, 2001) and *ARToolkit* (Kato and Billingham, 1999). While these toolkits provide a good platform for further development by experts, they are by no means usable by non-expert designers. It would be analogue to providing product designers with a GUI toolkit to develop Photoshop, instead of just giving them Photoshop.

CONTRIBUTION

The non-exhaustive review of the history and state of the art of VR in the product development process emphasises the difference between *applications* of VR and the *tools* that create the application. While research established a substantial set of advantageous VR applications facilitating various design tasks, there is a lack of tools suitable for use by product designers; research and development tools or toolkits can not be used by product designers directly.

We address this knowledge gap by gathering requirements for the development of useful and usable VR design tools for product designers. The resulting requirements can subsequently be used to create VR design tools that match designers' capabilities and respect existing design tool chains.

PRELIMINARY STUDY

The current research is part of a larger project in which four industrial partners are involved. These partners represent various fields of design, including automotive, mechatronics, electronics and mechanical systems design. Prior to involving the

industrial partners in actual case studies, a preliminary study was carried out to investigate the current perception of VR within the companies, and to create a shared basic understanding of VR. Similar to the work of Cobb et al, 1995, the preliminary study involved a series of in-depth interviews and site visits, and a one day VR demonstration session aiming to provide the involved industries with an overview of VR opportunities for the early stages of product development.

INTERVIEWS AND SITE VISITS

The first part of the preliminary study involved a series of in-depth interviews with engineers, managers and designers from the four different companies¹.

The use of VR within the companies was found to be limited to one meeting room with a stereoscopic display and the use of CAD systems. Nevertheless, interviewees acknowledged the potential benefits of applying VR in the product development process. It was however difficult for the participants to translate the envisioned future VR applications into concrete requirements. The same finding was reported by Cobb et al, 1995, where participants “*had difficulty expressing and developing ideas for specific applications of a technology they had little experience of*”.

DEMONSTRATION SESSION

A VR demo session was organised to provide the company representatives with more concrete manifestations of VR applications and consequently elicit more detailed feedback. The session involved representatives from the four companies also involved in the interviews. Participants were shown various forms of VR technologies being used in design applications, including an augmented reality factory layout application (see figure 1), an immersive drive simulator, a 3D virtual usability test lab and a 3D interactive ‘experience’ lab. As a result, the four different companies were able to see and discuss each others interpretation of how VR could be used in the product development process.

Figure 1. Augmented reality application shown during the VR demo session. The application allows designers to move around virtual machines normally situated in a factory environment.

The session ended with a group discussion about how to actually create these applications (i.e. how to make the step from *application* to *tool*). Participants pointed out that in the early stages of development, it is important to be able to work quickly, as creativity can not easily be predicted or guided. It was found to be important for VR design tools to be operated directly by designers, instead of being facilitated by an external company. Furthermore, designers are fond of their tools and very skilled in using them. Ideally, VR design tools should therefore fit existing tool chains rather than replace them.

RESULTS

The first part of the preliminary study made clear that while designers generally acknowledge the potential benefits of VR in the early stage of the design process, it is difficult for them to express concrete requirements or expectations. In the second part of the preliminary study we used the VR demo session to provide product designers with a first ‘hands-on’ experience with VR applications. The positive response to the demo session advocates the use of a ‘hands-on’ and application oriented approach to actively engage product designers in identifying design tool requirements. This approach is further introduced in the next section.

1. Conducted in the Netherlands, between November 2009 and March 2010. Each company study involved about 10-12 one hour interviews.

T3 VR Solution specifically designed for this company

t3 VR Solution translated to other companies' process

Figure 2. Research outline. The diagram illustrates the sequence of three case studies. Each case study involves one industrial partner for which a VR application and tool will be created. A cross-company evaluation is conducted after each case study (shown by the horizontal bars) to validate and generalize the case study results.

RESEARCH OUTLINE

The primary objective of this research is to identify requirements for the development of usable and useful VR design tools. From the preliminary study it was concluded that defining such requirements requires *involvement of product designers* and an *application oriented* approach.

Involvement of product designers is achieved through three sequential industrial case studies. The three companies represent various design disciplines, including automotive, mechatronics, and mechanical systems design².

As shown in figure 2, each of these case studies involves the following steps.

- **Identify Applications** - Participants are introduced to a wide range of VR technologies and their application in the product development process. Guided by the researcher (e.g. through workshops) the participants match technologies to potential opportunities in their company's product development process.

- **Create Design Tool** - With the application in mind, the researcher provides the participants with VR design tools (by selecting, combining or adapting existing tools, or by developing new tool prototypes) that enable designers to create and use the envisioned application.
- **Deploy & Evaluate Design Tool** - Participants use the VR design tool in a test case, and evaluate the design tool as well as the resulting application (e.g. does the application indeed offer the anticipated added value, and does the tool allow us to easily create the application?).

The application of VR and the accompanying design tools resulting from the first two steps are tailor-made for the specific company, meaning that the design tool requirements derived from these results are in principle valid for this specific case only. To extend the validity of these requirements, the results of each case study will be validated and generalised by conducting a cross-company evaluation, as indicated by the lower horizontal bars in figure 2. Here the main question is how well the application and tool can be translated to contexts in other companies. For instance, a tool may perfectly

2. These are three of the four companies also involved in the interviews and demonstration sessions of the preliminary study.

fit the tool chain of company A, but require modifications to also work for company B. Doing these cross-company evaluations for all three case studies will lead to insights in the validity of design tool requirements across industries.

The next section highlights results from the first case study and reflects on the proposed research approach.

CASE STUDY

The first case study involves designers from a multinational manufacturer of printers and copiers. The participating designers are all part of the Research & Development department of this company, but range from visual designers to usability experts and interaction designers. The following sub sections outline the results of the first case study, focusing on the '*Identification of VR Applications*'. While this step is intended as a preparation for identifying actual tool requirements (as explained in the previous section), it was found to be more relevant than expected and therefore interesting to highlight in this paper.

IDENTIFY APPLICATIONS

The first part of the case study aims to define a useful application of VR within the design process of the participating company. This requires collective in-depth knowledge of the company's design process and knowledge of the available VR technologies. A group workshop was organised in which company participants provide the former, and the researcher provides the latter. In order for both parties to understand each other, a common language was created in the form of visual storyboards.

Storyboards

The use of visual storyboards was inspired by various participatory design methods such as *Inspiration Cards* (Halskov and Dalsgård, 2006), *Pivots* (Urnes et al, 2002) and the *Future Technology Workshop* (Vavoula et al, 2002).

In a one-day workshop we first asked designers to describe regular design activities in visual storyboards. The storyboards were made of paper 'frames' that visually depict parts of an activity such as working at a desk, interviewing an end-user or discussions with fellow designers. Participants used

Figure 3. One of the storyboards created during the group workshop.

these frames to create their own storyboards (see figure 3). After describing the regular activities, the designers were given 'technology frames' depicting various VR technologies, such as augmented reality, haptic devices or motion tracking. The designers were asked to add these frames to their storyboards wherever they seemed to fit. The participants first created individual storyboards, which were merged into four group storyboards after a round of presentation and discussion.

Initial Application Outline

The four resulting group storyboards visualise different situations in the design process where VR applications are considered useful. For instance, one of the storyboards describes the use of augmented reality to allow end-users to see virtual future copiers in their own office. Another storyboard describes the use of VR to support detailed design of machine components by allowing engineers to inspect the future product in virtual reality. The contribution of the storyboard workshop lies not in the novelty of these applications, but rather in giving VR technologies a familiar context, which makes it easier for designers to identify and discuss requirements for the application. After a review, a discussion and voting round there was consensus about which application to focus on. The designers envision a virtual environment in which a virtual product concept can be tested by end-users. A physical environment for this purpose is already available within the company, but it does not resemble the typical use context of end-users (e.g. print shops). A realistic virtual use context is

expected to trigger more reliable behaviour and feedback from a test-user during a concept evaluation.

APPLICATION REFINEMENT

The application resulting from the workshop provides designers with a reference from which they can express requirements regarding VR design tools. For instance, they can make a founded estimation of how much time is available for using the tools, or what features the tools should provide in order to create the application.

For certain requirements however, the application storyboards are not sufficient to base requirements on. In particular, the required *level of realism* of the virtual environment and the appropriate technical implementation, referred to as *level of virtuality*, are difficult to assess. Designers indicated a need to experience the effects of these parameters on the application before being able to express concrete tool requirements.

Hands-on Session

A one day hands-on session was organised to present four different implementations (prepared by the researcher) of the application that was originally envisioned. All four implementations consist of a virtual office environment in which designers and/or end-users can walk around and interact with objects, as shown in figure 4. The four implementations use two different levels of realism (high and low realism environments) and two different levels of virtuality (a fully virtual environment and an augmented reality environment). The fully virtual environment consists of a digital 3D virtual office that is projected on a large screen. Designers positioned in front of this screen use a keyboard and mouse to navigate a first-person perspective through the environment. The augmented reality environment consists of a tablet PC equipped with a camera. Pointing the tablet on a visual *marker* will display corresponding 3D models on the tablet's display. This allows designers to physically move around while exploring the augmented reality environment, pointing at specific markers.

Designers were asked to carry out a concept evaluation in each of the implementations, allowing them to experience the effects of different levels of

Figure 4. A screen shot of one of the virtual environments used in the application refinement session. This particular environment presents a fully virtual print-shop with a high level of realism.

realism and virtuality. Experiencing the four different application implementations helped designers with refining application requirements. For example, instead of simply requiring the highest level of realism, it was found that reduced realism (e.g. lower visual quality or objects not perfectly matching real-life objects) does not necessarily reduce the effectiveness of the application. Furthermore, the fully virtual environment was considered more effective for representing the use context. While the augmented reality environment did allow for more physical interactions (e.g. walking around an object), it failed to keep the designers 'immersed' in the virtual environment. The fully virtual environment was found to provide a more integral experience.

The hands-on experiences also helped with narrowing down the focus of the application. It was found that the application helps with analysing high-level task flows (e.g. end-users moving from one place in the office to another in order to operate a machine) rather than lower level interactions, such as user-machine interactions.

Towards Tool Requirements

The refined description of the VR application resulting from the hands-on session marks the border between the application oriented part and the tool oriented part of the case study. With the application clearly defined, the case study now focuses on determining which tools should be used to create the application, and how to let these tools fit the tool chains and skills available within the company.

TOOL SELECTION

To facilitate the translation of application experiences into tool requirements, the designers were shown the tools that were used for creating the four different application implementations. Each implementation involves a tool chain comprising of three development tasks, namely *Geometry Modeling* (the modeling of 3D objects), *Behaviour Modeling* (adding interactivity to objects) and *Scene Integration* (putting the objects in a 3D scene). The researcher explained how different tools used for each of these tasks lead to different levels of realism and virtuality. For instance, higher levels of realism require more complex modeling tools such as game engines, while low realism environments can be created with easy to use off-the-shelf interior design software. Sharing this information with designers enables them to assess the trade-offs between application characteristics and tool requirements, but also allows for a comparison between the VR tool chains and the tools already available within the company. Taking this information into account, the participating designers proposed two complementary tool chains for creating the envisioned VR applications.

- The first tool chain consists of only the *Geometry Modeling* and *Scene Integration* tasks. Designers indicated that *Geometry Modeling* tools and skills are already available in the company (e.g. CAD modeling departments), and that existing *Scene Integration* tools (the researcher demonstrated *SweetHome3D*, an interior design application) are expected to be sufficiently usable for designers. Applications resulting from this tool chain primarily target internal communication and marketing purposes; non-interactive 3D visualisations of future products in a certain context can help designers with communicating ideas to management or potential clients.
- The second tool chain proposed by the designers extends the above tool chain by adding tools for *Behaviour Modeling*. While this task is considered necessary for creating interactive virtual environments (e.g. a virtual printer model should be able to respond to user actions), the designers indicated that the task can be allocated to dedicated *prototypers* (designers trained in creating interactive software prototypes or

mockups), who are already available in the design department. Given their experience with software prototyping the *Behaviour Modeling* tools can focus on functionality and flexibility rather than ease of use. Applications resulting from this tool chain primarily target evaluation and analysis tasks in early stages of the design process; end-users can experience virtual product concepts in an interactive virtual use context.

These two tool chains resemble the current practice of the designers. When designers need a communication or marketing application, they typically want to be able to create it themselves. For the first VR tool chain this implies the re-use of existing CAD models and the availability of an easy to use *scene integration* tool.

The creation of interactive prototypes on the other hand, as for instance used for GUI usability evaluations, is typically allocated to dedicated prototypers. For the second VR tool chain this implies that designers need to be able to pass their non-interactive visualisations to the prototyper, who will extend the virtual environment into an interactive one using more advanced VR design tools. The results of the session show that, once provided with a concrete VR application and basic knowledge of tools, designers are able to identify opportunities for re-using available resources (e.g. CAD model repositories) and able to pin-point potential bottlenecks in the tool chains (e.g. the need for easy to use *scene integration* tools for designers, and *behaviour modeling* tools for prototypers). The final part of the case study will address these potential bottlenecks. For the *scene integration* task off-the-shelf tools will be evaluated to see whether or not they are usable by all people from the design department. For the *behaviour modeling* task tools are to be found that match the skills of the dedicated prototypers.

CONCLUSION

VR technologies offer various advantageous applications for, in particular the early stages of, the product design process. However, VR development tools needed to build the applications in existing form do not match the skills and requirements of designers. The research presented in this paper proposes a user-centered and application-oriented

approach for developing more useful and usable VR design tools for product designers.

The presented case study demonstrates the benefits of identifying a VR application before discussing tool requirements. A concrete VR application helps the designers with maintaining a focus and consequently provides more detailed tool requirements. Defining a useful VR application was however more challenging than expected. The storyboards created during the group workshop were useful for outlining the application, but an additional hands-on session was needed to further refine the application before being able to elicit detailed tool requirements. This session provided the participants with sufficient hands-on experience to translate application characteristics to tool requirements, and to identify bottlenecks in the resulting VR design tool chain.

While the approach outlined in this paper has been quite successful in our first case study, the outcome of the remaining two case studies is expected to provide more detailed insights in the potential limitations and challenges of the approach.

FUTURE WORK

Upon completion, the results of the first case study will be evaluated in a cross-company evaluation. To do so, the researcher will show the participating companies how the current company-specific implementation could be applied in another company context. This in turn allows the companies to reflect on the tool requirements derived from the case study, or add requirements based on their own perspectives.

On a longer term, the remaining two case studies will be carried out, following a procedure similar to the one presented in this paper. After completing all three case studies (and their cross-company evaluation sessions), a generalisation of all tool requirements can be made.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors gratefully acknowledge the support of the Innovation-Oriented Research Programme 'Integral Product Creation and Realization (IOP IPCR)' of the Netherlands Ministry of Economic Affairs, Agriculture and Innovation.

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